

Influence of Teacher Certification Benefits and Discipline Toward Teacher Performance in Elementary Schools of Gorontalo City

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Abstract

The research aims to investigate the influence of teacher certification benefits towards teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City, the influence of discipline towards teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City, and the influence of teacher certification benefits and discipline teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City. This research uses a quantitative method with a descriptive approach, revealing one variable's influence on another. The population in this research are teachers receiving certification at the Elementary School of Gorontalo City, consisting of 523 people, while the sample was 130 people. Data is collected through the distribution of questionnaires. The findings reveal that the independent variables obtained information that the teacher's certification benefits (X1) have an influence toward performance (Y) of 0.2452 or 24.52% and discipline (X2) has an influence toward teacher performance (Y) of 0.2072 or 20.72%. Simultaneously (X1) and (X2) have an influence toward (Y) of 45.24%. This research concludes that teacher certification benefits and discipline partially and simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance in elementary schools in Gorontalo City. With the evidence that certification and discipline can improve teacher performance significantly, it is suggested (1) that the Gorontalo City Education Office is more intense in socializing and overseeing the implementation of teacher professional allowance criteria. (2) The school implements a teacher attendance system using fingerprints to obtain authentic data regarding attendance. (3) Teachers can improve the implementation of their duties as educators.

Keywords: Performance, Certification benefits, and Discipline.

Introduction

High-quality education is an integral concept encompassing diverse aspects to ensure that the education provided not only imparts knowledge but also shapes the character, skills, and values necessary for leading a meaningful life. The relevance of quality education to SDGs' fourth goal (Quality Education) is key to achieving overall sustainable development objectives. Quality education can contribute to realizing other SDG goals, such as reducing poverty, narrowing inequalities, and improving health and well-being.

Table 1: Quality Achievement in Literacy Aspect

	% Students in education units		Bobot	Index	
proficient	4.44%	0.04	3	0.133	2,10 - 3.00
capably	51.11%	0.51	2	1.02	1,80 - 2.09
Basic	35.56%	0.36	1.5	0.53	1,40 - 1,79
PIK	8.89%	0.09	1	0.09	1,00 - 1,39
	1.00	1.00		1.78	under minimum competence

Source: Education Office of Gorontalo City

The teacher is an important executor of learning because the teacher's will be directly related to students. about Teachers and Lecturers, states "Teachers are professional educators who have the main obligations of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, and assessing students in the early childhood learning process in official learning channels, basic learning, as well as intermediate learning (*Undang-Undang RI No. 14 Tentang Guru Dan Dosen*, 2005). 1.00 1.00 1.78 Below minimum competency. Reliable teachers must have a minimum academic qualification of expert, be competent, physically and mentally healthy, and have expertise in creating learning goals nationally. For teachers to be able to carry out their duties well, performance must be improved. teacher performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (the results of activities achieved by a person). So according to the language ability can be meant as a visible result as a form of successful activity in a person.

However, if you look closely, there are still many teachers who have abandoned efforts to improve their performance. This matter applies to elementary school teachers in the City of Gorontalo. The problems that occur in the City of Gorontalo :(1) the lack of teacher seminar activities regarding the curriculum because each teacher can only conduct seminars every year; (2) the limited infrastructure tools cause teachers to be less competent in studying learning; (3) Government Regulation No. 53 Regarding Discipline not implemented; (4) some

teachers have not been able to carry out the programming process; (5) teacher professionalism is still lacking in the learning process; and (6) there is an assumption that the teacher's work is only a means of earning income, the less than the optimal ability of teachers can be seen in the results of the 2021 National Assessment as follows:

Table 2: Quality Achievement in Numeracy aspects

	% Students in education units		Bobot	Index	
proficient	0%	0.000	3	0	2,10 - 3.00
capably	33.33%	0.333	2	0.67	1,80 - 2.09
Basic	62.22%	0.622	1.5	0.93	1,40 - 1,79
PIK	4.44%	0.044	1	0.04	1,00 - 1,39
	1.00	1.00		1.64	under minimum competence

Source: Education Office of Gorontalo City

The achievement of the assessment results for literacy and numeracy is still very low at the minimum competency, this shows that teacher performance still needs to be improved. Various aspects affect teachers' abilities, one of which is teacher certification assistance. Derived from the government's goal of creating a national learning system in the maximum way, it requires teachers to have good competence and professionalism. This is also stated in Law No. 20/2003 concerning the National Education System article 39 part 2, RI Law No. 14/2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, and PP RI No. 19/2005 concerning National Education Standards which underwent the last transformation to become PP RI No. 57/2005. 2021. Based on this regulation, the teaching staff must have minimum expert learning qualifications and obtain a professional teaching certificate. These 2 indicators, especially professional certificates, are an important perspective in measuring the level of readiness and professionalism of a teacher. The presence of a teacher, especially a teacher contributes to improving the quality of learning. This will happen when teachers have good quality, are prosperous, dignified, and reliable.

As a form of appreciation and appreciation, the government provides a special budget to teachers who meet the requirements of being professional teachers. The appreciation is certification assistance. Certification or professional assistance is one type of income that is given to teachers who already have a teaching certificate.

According to the information obtained from the manager of the teacher certification fund, namely the personnel development sector of the Gorontalo City Education Office, the data above all receive certification benefits, because they can administratively fulfill the requirements in eligibility to receive these allowances. Meanwhile, in reality, it is assumed that not all of the recipients of certification have met the performance standards, as the results

of an interview with (A; Principal of SDN 60 Kota Gorontalo) informed that the professional allowance will still be received because remembering that the Principal does not want problems with the recipient and does not even want to be considered by the Principal too harshly, The point is that professional allowances have not had a positive impact on performance and discipline results, and he suggests that there can be teacher transfers taking into account the zoning of residence. This statement was reinforced by (D.H; Principal of SDN 82 Kota Gorontalo) that in terms of giving grades, conflicts often occur when there are teachers who are not qualified to object and want the principal to give good grades. To avoid conflicts, sometimes the school principal immediately gives good grades to all certification recipients (assessment is still subjective).

Various attempts have been made to overcome the above problems, especially in improving discipline, including through the school principal's supervision program, especially teaching attendance in class. This responsibility is generally the principal's role as a top leader, although each individual has a role. Efforts to improve discipline can be carried out by the school through 1) supervising work rules for teachers, 2) strict application of discipline and imposing sanctions, 3) exemplary discipline in attitude, and 4) providing facilities to support teacher discipline (Tatoe, 2019). However, the problem of discipline is still a problem that is difficult to resolve, the statement (A. Principal of SDN 60 Kota Gorontalo) informs recipients that they are often late for the reason that they live far away so the impact of being late learning services and the community is often highlighted, furthermore from D.H. Principal of SDN 82 Information was obtained from the City of Gorontalo that the recapitulation of monthly attendance reached 85%, meaning that 15% of teachers were absent due to illness and a little undisciplined.

Teacher discipline data from observations at schools include; SDN 41 Hulonthalangi, City of Gorontalo, the number of teachers is 29 people. From the attendance list in 1 month, it can be seen that 18 people are often late, or around 62%, 24 people often do not fill in the morning and evening attendance list, or around 82%, and go home early, 18 people go home quickly; SDN 91 Sipatana, City of Gorontalo, the number of teachers is 11 people, it can be seen that they were listed as attending in June 2022, the percentage of teachers who often asked for permission was around 9.09%, they were sick 2% and for SDN 60 Kota Timur Kota Gorontalo, it was seen that 100% attendance was confirmed. no absences appear to be late and or negligent, according to the statement of the school principal that since there is no longer any enforcement of monthly reports, the attendance list is recapitulated later during the certification filing. This is in line with the statement by the headmaster of SDN 59 Kota Timur that the teacher attendance list was not questioned during school accreditation, so it seemed as if it had gone unnoticed except for the fulfillment of the certification documents.

In addition to time discipline, in reality in the field there are still many teachers who receive certification benefits but have not fully demonstrated administrative discipline, the narrative from (D.H. Principal of SDN 82 Gorontalo City) that teacher performance is measured by making learning tools starting with program planning, learning processes and evaluation, in general, all fulfilled, but there are some teachers who in one indicator are considered less like in the learning process, this is due to the non-linear basic of education, for example, the Physical Education teacher (PJOK) is certified as a class teacher, and a religion teacher is also

a certified class teacher. The second cause is the lack of IT Presidency that the learning process becomes hampered.

Methods

This research is used quantitative research. Quantitative research is a research methodology built on a positivist philosophy to study populations or specific examples, use research tools to collect data, and analyze quantitative or statistical information to measure assumptions made (Sugiyono, 2017) . The research was conducted at Elementary Schools in the City of Gorontalo.

The population obtained in this research is all elementary school teachers who receive certification benefits in the City of Gorontalo. For 2022 there are 523 people. While the sample in this research was 130 people. The sample is representative of the population being monitored. If the total population is not more than 100 people, all samples must be used, but if the total population exceeds 100 people, the sample collection can be 10 to 15% or 20 to 25% of the entire population (Arikunto, 2016). Looking at the overall population of this research, there are 523 people so the sample collection is 25%. The techniques of collecting data in this research used observation, questionnaires, and documentation.

Results

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1979.20	2	989.60	52.391	.000 ^b
Residual	0		0		
Total	2398.869	127	18.889		
	4378.069	129			

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Discipline, Teacher Certification Benefits

The results of the F-count experiment obtained a F-count of 52.391 greater than a F-table of 3.07 and a degree of significance of 0.000. Based on the F experiment it proved a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	5.427	5.922		.916	.361
Teacher Certification	.471	.078	.428	6.021	.000
Benefits					
Discipline	1.738	.324	.381	5.358	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 6.021 which is greater than the table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment, it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variable Teacher Certification benefits

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 5.358 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance

Hypothesis Testing

- a. Influence of Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously has a positive and significant influence on performance (Y)

The results of the F-count experiment obtained a F-count of 52.391 greater than a F-table of 3.07 and a degree of significance of 0.000. Based on the F experiment it proved a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance.

This means that the reported assumption that Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

- b. Teacher Certification benefits (X1) Partially Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Teacher Performance (Y)

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 6.021 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment, it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variable Teacher Certification benefits

(X1) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance.

This means that the reported assumption that the Teacher Certification benefits (X1) partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

- c. Discipline (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y)

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 5.358 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. This means that the assumption that reports that Discipline (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

Discussion

1. The simultaneous influence of teacher certification benefits and discipline on teacher performance

Respondents' assumptions about teacher performance variables, in general, are very high, it seems that respondents who respond very highly are able to organize learning concepts well. Respondents who responded very high to be able to do well in learning. Respondents who responded very high to be able to calculate the results of the student or student practice. Respondents who responded very highly were able to follow up on the results of evaluating the results of a student or student practice. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the basic goals of education well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the learning procedure well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the level of progress of students well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the appropriate learning approach to the upgrading module. Respondents responded very highly to practicing cooperation in the profession well. Respondents responded very highly to the use of science and technology developments in learning. Respondents responded very highly to understanding the knowledge and skills according to the upgrading module. Respondents who responded very highly to improve their work well.

The results of the regression calculation between certification and discipline allowance variables and performance variables prove that teacher certification assistance and discipline simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. This means that the reported assumption that teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously have a positive and meaningful impact on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

The research results match the results of research conducted, stated that there was an important influence of professional allowances and the discipline of teacher activities together on teacher performance (Elien et al., 2020). stated that certification assistance and work discipline affect teacher performance (Nurjannah et al., 2021).

2. Partial influence of teacher certification benefits on teacher performance (Y)

Respondents' assumptions on the teacher certification benefits variable in general, respondents reported as very high. Teacher Certification benefits (X1) Respondents who responded to the amount of certification assistance according to the last level of education, were in the very high category. Respondents responded that teachers who receive certification

benefits must attend competency and certification education and training, which are in the very high category. Respondents who responded to teachers who received certification benefits were viewed based on the length of time being a teacher, which was in the high category. Respondents who respond to teachers who receive certification benefits must have the expertise to organize learning implementation plans (RPP) in an analytical way which is in the Very High category. Respondents who responded that teachers received certification benefits were based on evaluations from leaders and supervisors while in class and in the school area which were in the very high category. Respondents who responded that teachers receiving certification benefits needed to have expertise in improving their quality as teaching staff in the very high category. Respondents who responded that teachers receiving certification benefits needed to explore objective forum activities in the high category. Respondents who responded to teachers who received certification benefits were observed to be based on results and appreciation that were relevant to their academic aspects which were in the high category.

The results of the regression calculation between the certification benefits variable and the teacher performance variable prove that the teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher achievement. This means that the assumption that reports that teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

This is in line with the study of (Elien et al., 2020) stating that there is a significant impact of professional allowances on teacher performance. Teacher certification has no influence on teacher performance (Bister, 2016). teacher certification benefits can partially explain performance (Noer, 2018). stated that certification benefits do not affect teacher performance (Nurjannah et al., 2021).

3. The influence of discipline partially on teacher performance (Y)

Respondents' assumptions on disciplinary factors, in general, are really big. Respondents reported teacher discipline to school rules in the very high category.

Respondents who responded to the accuracy of the teacher's duration in the school area were in the very high section. Respondents who responded to understanding the teacher in carrying out his duties lie in a very high type. Respondents who responded that teachers are required to have a responsibility in carrying out their duties are in the very high category.

The results of the regression calculation between the disciplinary variable and the teacher performance variable prove that the disciplinary variable partially has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. This means that the assumption that reports that discipline partially has a positive and meaningful influence on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

This is in line with the opinions of stating that there are important consequences of teacher work discipline on teacher performance (Elien et al., 2020). Work discipline has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance (Bister, 2016). Work discipline

affects teacher performance, state that works discipline has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher achievement (Wiwin & Mukhtar, 2018)

Employee discipline is a form of training that seeks to justify and create insights, actions, and behavior of employees so that employees sincerely try to work cooperatively with other employees and improve their work results.

If discipline is the description and desire of a person to comply with all company regulations and legitimate social norms (Hasibuan, 2019). The explanation is the activity of someone who honestly obeys the rules and remembers the roles and responsibilities. So, he will obey or carry out all his duties properly, not on impulse. Desire is an action, behavior, and behavior of a person in accordance with company regulations, whether registered or not. From this explanation, it appears that discipline must be upheld in an institution. Without the support of good employee discipline, it is difficult for the institution to achieve its goals so that employee discipline is one of the keys to the success of an institution or industry in achieving its goals

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the results of the data processing carried out, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the questionnaire variables X1 and X2 were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis shows that the Fcount value is 52.391 which is greater than the Ftable of 3.07 and has a significant level of 0.000. Based on the F test, it shows a significant level of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, the statistical variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (ANOVA). This means that the assumption that reports that teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are **Accepted**.
2. The teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the Certification benefits variable questionnaire were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis It can be seen that the results of the t-count test are 6.021, which is greater than the t-table of 1.656 and has a significant level of 0.000. Based on the t-test shows that the significant level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, the statistical variable Teacher Certification benefits (X1) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Coefficients). This means that the reported assumption that teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is **Accepted**.

3. Discipline variables in a partial way have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the Discipline variable questionnaire were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis results obtained a tcount of 5.358 greater than the ttable of 1.656, and a significant level of 0.000. Based on the t-test shows that the significant level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Coefficients). This means that the reported assumption that discipline partially has a positive and significant influence on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is **Accepted**.

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